

The Doctrine of Śakti in Vīraśaiva Philosophy: A Study of Śrīpati and Śrīkaṅṭha

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Abstract: The Vīraśaiva or Liṅgāyat tradition of medieval South India presents a distinct philosophical system known as Śakti-viśiṣṭādvaita. This doctrine establishes a non-dual metaphysics centered on the relationship between Śiva (the Supreme Brahman), His inherent Śakti (power), and the Aṅga (individual soul). Through the lens of Vimarśa-śakti (reflective consciousness)—a concept drawing structural parallels to Kashmir Śaivism—Śiva manifests and governs the universe via five primary forms of energy: Cit, Ānanda, Icchā, Jñāna, and Kriyā-śakti. The path to liberation (Vīramārga) emphasizes devotion, niṣkāma karma (selfless action), and the Ṣaṣṭhala (six-stage spiritual pathway). This process aligns the soul's experience with the three symbolic dimensions of the Divine:

- Bhāva-liṅga (Sat / Existence)
- Prāṇa-liṅga (Cit / Consciousness)
- Iṣṭa-liṅga (Ānanda / Bliss)

Ultimately, liberation is realized as the complete identity and non-difference between the power-qualified individual soul (Aṅga-sthala) and the power-qualified Divine (Liṅga-sthala).

Keywords: Parā-śakti, Vimarśa-śakti, Liṅga-sthala, Aṅga-sthala, Manifestation.

Introduction

In Vedānta there are many branches such as Advaita, Viśiṣṭādvaita, Śuddhādvaita, Dvaita, Kevalādvaita and Acintya-bhedābheda. Among the Śaivas too, even those who are non-dualists exhibit considerable doctrinal diversity. One of the important Śaiva sects that emerged and developed in medieval South India is the Vīraśaiva or Liṅgāyat tradition. Compared to other established Śaiva sects, they appear to be relatively late in origin; for Mādhavācārya in the *Sarvadārśanasāgraha* discussed the Nakulīśa Pāsupata and Āgamānta Śaiva systems, but made no mention of the Vīraśaivas. They are not referred to in the works of Śaṅkarācārya, Ānandagiri or Vācaspati Mīśra.

The Vīraśaivas fundamentally uphold a doctrine of Śakti-viśiṣṭādvaita (qualified non-dualism endowed with power), though the doctrine is known by five different names: Śivādvaita, Dvaitādvaita, Vīraśaiva, Viśeṣādvaita and Śakti-viśiṣṭādvaita. This Śakti-qualified non-dualism is action-oriented. Believing in niṣkāma karma (desireless action), their path is called Vīradharma or Vīramārga. According to this tradition, liberation consists in the harmonious union or identity of the power-qualified individual soul and the power-qualified Śiva.¹

Since they wear the Śiva-liṅga on the body, they are called Liṅgāyats. They were also socially known as “Vīraśivas.” The best-known teacher of this tradition is Basava, whose name is the Kannada form of the Sanskrit word *vṛṣabha*. He was a Karnataka Brāhmaṇa from Bāgevāḍi, son of Mādirāja. Extraordinary spiritual powers manifested in him from an early age. Although he himself wrote no books, his sayings and sermons became famous within the Vīraśaiva tradition. Some scholars believe that this Śaiva sect had originated one or two centuries before the twelfth century CE, later declined for a time, and was revitalized and popularized in society by Basava.

Śakti: According to Śrīpati

In the *Siddhāntaśikhamaṇi*, which expounds the doctrine of Śrīpati, the ety-

mology of “Vīraśaiva” is explained as follows: “Vī” signifies knowledge that grants awareness of the non-difference between Śiva and the jīva; “ra” denotes one who delights or becomes absorbed. Thus, one who enables delight in the identity of Śiva and the soul is called a Vīraśaiva².

According to them, the one non-dual Supreme Brahman, whose nature is Sat-Cit-Ānanda, is Śiva-tattva. Another name for it is *Sthala*. It is believed that within this Śiva-tattva lies the causal seed of the entire manifested universe beginning with Mahat; and at dissolution the whole cosmos arising from prakṛti and puruṣa again merges into that Śiva-tattva. Hence Śiva is called *Sthala*. Through the agitation of the power residing within Him, He divides into two aspects: Liṅga-sthala and Aṅga-sthala. Liṅga-sthala is the worshipful Rudra-Śiva, while Aṅga-sthala is the individual soul or worshipper.

The power residing within Śiva divides itself into two forms by its own will: Kalā and Bhakti. Kalā abides in Śiva, whereas Bhakti manifests as the means of uplifting the soul and becomes the liberating force. Bhakti acts as the bridge connecting Liṅga-sthala (Śiva) and Aṅga-sthala (the individual soul). Liṅga-sthala has three divisions: Bhāva-liṅga, Prāṇa-liṅga and Iṣṭa-liṅga, also known respectively as Niṣkala, Sakala-niṣkala and Sakala. Bhāva-liṅga represents the Sat aspect of Supreme Śiva; Prāṇa-liṅga represents Cit; and Iṣṭa-liṅga manifests Ānanda. Among these, Bhāva-liṅga, identified with pure Being, is regarded as the highest principle. Prāṇa-liṅga is its subtle form, while Iṣṭa-liṅga is its gross manifestation. Associated with mantra, ritual and practice, Bhāva-liṅga becomes Kalā, Prāṇa-liṅga manifests as Nāda, and Iṣṭa-liṅga becomes Bindu. Each of these three principles again has two subdivisions. Bhāva-liṅga is divided into Mahāliṅga and Prasāda-liṅga; Prāṇa-liṅga into Cara-liṅga and Siva-liṅga; and Iṣṭa-liṅga into Guru-liṅga and Ācāra-liṅga. Another name for these liṅgas is Ṣaṭsthala. The self together with the five elements constitutes Ṣaṭsthala. According to this cosmology, during creation space arises from the self, then air from space, fire from air, water from fire, and earth from water.

These six liṅgas of Śiva are animated by six forms of Śakti: Cit-śakti, Parāśakti, Ādi-śakti, Icchā-śakti, Jñāna-śakti and Kriyā-śakti. Śivayogī Śivācārya recognized two forms of Śakti in the Vīraśaiva system: Parāśakti, full of Sat-Cit-Ānanda, and another qualified by guṇas and established in Brahman. Though Śakti is one, it exists in two modes: undivided contemplation and differentiated contemplation. In the first अवस्था, Śakti abides like Paramaśiva Himself as pure Sat-Cit-Ānanda; in the second, the experience of the manifestation of Sat-Cit-Ānanda in Paramaśiva is called Śiva’s Śakti—namely Cit-śakti.

Without awareness of the Sat-Cit-Ānanda nature of Paramaśiva, Śiva would become inert like a crystal lacking consciousness. Therefore, Śivācārya worships Śiva together with Cit-śakti. In this respect the doctrine resembles Kashmir Śaivism, where Paramaśiva is described as the reflective awareness (*vimarśa*) of Śakti. Their statement is: “Manifestation is not separate from प्रकाश (light), and that light is not separate from reflective awareness.”³ Without Vimarśa-śakti, Śiva would become powerless and inert, according to Kṣemarāja.⁴

The Vīraśaivas also accept Parāśakti as the independent power of the Supreme Lord. By means of this undifferentiated consciousness-power the Lord sustains, perceives and manifests the universe from Śiva down to the earth.⁵ This Parāśakti is pure consciousness itself.⁶ The autonomous Cit-śakti becomes the infi-

nite universe⁷ while remaining non-different from Śiva⁸. Śiva's Cit-śakti shines forth in infinite forms, with innumerable names and manifestations.

Ācārya Jayaratha states that the entire diversity of sentient and insentient existence, the five cosmic acts—creation, preservation, dissolution, concealment and grace—and the four states of consciousness—waking, dream, deep sleep and tūrīya—are all manifestations of Śiva's power.⁹

Śrīkaṇṭha's Doctrine of Śiva and Śakti

Śrīkaṇṭha Śivācārya was also a Śaiva Viśiṣṭādvaitin; therefore, the doctrines of Śakti according to Śrīpati and Śrīkaṇṭha deserve consideration. According to Śrīkaṇṭha, Śiva is the Saguna Brahman, the personal God. He is the "I"-principle, Sat-Cit-Ānanda, and the Supreme Self. On one hand He transcends the universe; on the other He is the material cause of the physical world. By His own power He creates the universe.

Śiva's Śakti is Umā, the supreme Prakṛti and Parāśakti. She is also identified with Praṇava (Om).¹⁰ The unsurpassed knowledge and bliss that constitute Brahman are inseparable from His power.¹¹ The commentator on the *Śivār-kamaṇḍīpikā* explains that the word Śakti refers to the supreme power constituting Śiva-hood itself.¹² Thus Śiva's very divinity is His Parāśakti. Yet Śrīkaṇṭha also maintains that Śakti is both identical with and distinct from Śiva.¹³

Śakti is of two kinds: Cit-śakti and Jaḍa-śakti. United with these two, Śiva becomes the conscious and unconscious universe.¹⁴ Both conscious and material powers are natural to Śiva¹⁵ and may even be regarded as His attributes.¹⁶

Śrīkaṇṭha further identifies Parāprakṛti with Cit-śakti. The Upaniṣads describe Brahman as having space as His body,¹⁷ and according to the *Kūrma Purāṇa*, "space" here signifies Cit-śakti.¹⁸ Thus Cit-śakti is the body of Brahman and pervades the entire universe. Creation is a transformation of this very power.

Śiva's Jaḍa-śakti is Māyā,¹⁹ the material principle underlying the five elements.²⁰ Mahādeva is the possessor of Māyā,²¹ and therefore Māyā eternally resides in Him. Śiva is thus eternally associated with Māyā and thereby becomes the material cause of creation. The world cannot arise from Māyā alone, nor from Śiva alone; creation requires the union of Śiva and Śakti.²²

Śrīkaṇṭha does not accept an abstract undifferentiated Brahman divorced from Umā. Rather, the Supreme Reality must be understood as Umā together with Umāpati.²³ Yet although united, Umā is also called Māyā because of relational distinction. Nevertheless, this Māyā is pure.

Śiva endowed with subtle consciousness and matter is the causal state, while Śiva endowed with gross consciousness and matter is the manifested effect.²⁴ Thus the world is non-different from Śiva as effect from cause. Yet Śiva Himself does not literally transform into the world; rather, His Māyā becomes the material basis of the universe.

Determination of Śakti-viśiṣṭādvaita

Śrīpati, the exponent of Śakti-viśiṣṭādvaita, holds that Śiva expands His power to create the universe. The world is the very nature of Śiva. Śiva is the material cause of creation, and in this respect Śrīpati agrees with Śrīkaṇṭha. Without dependence on any external instrument, Śiva creates everything.

Śrīpati, like Śaṅkara, regards Śiva as both the efficient and material cause of the universe and uses the analogy of the spider spinning its web. Though the efficient and material causes are non-different, they are not absolutely identical. Śiva as creator is always endowed with Śakti. Before creation, the world exists within

Parāśakti. Śiva in the form of Śakti is the material cause, while Śiva in His transcendent aspect is the efficient cause. Śrīpati accepts the identity of Śakti and Śaktimān. Śiva is simultaneously the possessor of power, constituted by power, and the lord of power. Between Śiva and Śakti there exists a relation of essential identity (*tādātmya*). Worship of Śiva in both his conscious and material forms lead the soul to liberation.

According to Śrīpati, scriptural study alone cannot lead to realization of Brahman; the grace of Śiva and the Guru is indispensable. Through the combined path of knowledge and devotion the realization of Brahman becomes possible, and in liberation the individual soul becomes united with Śiva.

Conclusion

A comparative discussion of the Śaiva Viśiṣṭādvaita systems of Śrīkaṇṭha and Śrīpati forms another important aspect of this study. Śrīkaṇṭha interprets Śiva and Umā as inseparable aspects of the Supreme Reality and regards creation as the manifestation of Śiva's power through Māyā and Cit-śakti. Śrīpati similarly upholds Śiva as both the material and efficient cause of the universe and emphasizes the essential identity of Śakti and Śaktimān. He further maintains that liberation is attained not merely through scriptural knowledge but through the combined grace of Śiva, Guru, devotion and spiritual realization.

The study concludes that Śakti-viśiṣṭādvaita presents a profound and dynamic vision of reality in which Śiva, Śakti and the individual soul are integrated into a unified spiritual and metaphysical framework.

Endnotes

1. शक्तिश्च शक्तिश्च शक्ति, ताभ्यां विशिष्टौ जीवेशौ शक्तिविशिष्टौ तयोरद्वैतं शक्तिविशिष्टाद्वैतम्— Ed. Dwivedi Shyamakanta, *Kasmiriya Saivadarsana and Spandashastra*, Chawkhamba Surabharati Prakasana, Varanasi, 2009, 4th chapter, p.136.
2. वीशब्देनोच्यते विद्या शिवजीवैक्यबोधिका।
3. तस्यां रमन्ते ये शैवा वीरशैवास्तु ते मताः॥-Śivayogi-śivacārya, *Śrīsiddhanta-sikhāmaṇiḥ*, 5.16.
4. Sing, Jaydev, *Vijñāna-vairava*, Motilal Bonarasidas, Varanasi, 1984, p.122.
5. यदि निर्विमर्शः स्याद अनीश्वरो जडश्च प्रसज्येत्—Shastri, Mukundarama, *The Para Praveshika of Kshemaraja*, Pratap Singh Bahadur, Jammu and Kashmir, 1918, p.2.
6. पराशक्तिः परमेश्वरी स्वातन्त्र्यशक्तिः।-Kṣemaraja, *Pratyavijñāhṛdayam*, explained by Sudhanshu Kumar Sarangi, Chawkhamba Surabharati Prakasana, Varanasi, 2017, p. 68.
7. यया इदं शिवादिघरण्यन्तम अतिकल्प-संविन्मात्ररूपतया विभर्ति च पश्यति च भासयति च परमेश्वरः सा अस्य श्रीपराशक्तिः।-*Tantrasāra*, p.28.
8. *Pratyavijñāhṛdayam*, p.3.
9. *Ibid*, p.2.
10. एवं यत्किंचन जडजडाल्मकविश्ववैचित्र्यं, यच्च तद्विषयं सृष्ट्यादि जाग्रदाद्यवस्थादि वा ततसर्वं परमेश्वरस्य शक्तिस्फार एवा—*Tantraloka*, 1st Ahnika, p.121.
11. प्रणवपर्यायेणोमाशब्देन परप्रकृतिरूपा पराशक्तिरुच्यते।-*Brahmasutra*, 4.4.22, Srikantha-bhasya.
12. निरतिशय ज्ञानानन्दादिशक्ति महिमातिशयवत्तं हि ब्रह्मात्मम्—*ibid*, 1.1.1, Srikantha-bhasya.
13. शक्तिशब्देन शिवत्वरूपा पराशक्तिरुच्यते।-*ibid*, 2.2.38, Śivarkamaṇidīpikā.
14. *Bhāskarī*, Vol.3, introduction, p.154.
15. *Op.cit*.
16. चिदचित्प्रपंचरूपशक्तिविशिष्टत्वं स्वाभाविकमेव ब्रह्मणः।-*ibid*, 1.1.2.
17. *Ibid*.
18. *Ibid*, 1.2.1.
19. यस्या सा परमा देवी शक्तिराकाशसंचिता।-*ibid*, 1.1.2.

20. *Ibid*,1.1.1.
21. *Śvetāśvataropaniṣad*,4.10.
22. *Ibid*.
23. *Op.cit*,1.4.17
24. *Ibid*,1.1.25.
25. *Īśvarapratyavijñāvimarśinī*, Part-1,p.1

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